

Comparative Study of Binary and Ternary Complexes of Some Rare Earths

SANTOSH D. MAKHIJANI* and SATENDRA P. SANGAL**

Laxminarayan Institute of Technology, Nagpur University, Nagpur

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Modified form of Irving and Rossotti's pH titration technique has been used to evaluate and compare the stability constants of the binary and ternary complexes of Sc(III), Y(III), La(III), Pr(III), Nd(III) and Sm(III) at 30° at an ionic strength of 0.2M NaClO₄. For the study of ternary complexes, Nitrilotriacetic acid has been used as a primary ligand and polyhydroxy phenols, i.e., Pyrocatechol (PYC), Pyrogallol (PYG) and Gallic acid (GA) as secondary ligands. The stability constants of the binary complexes were found to be more than those of the corresponding ternary complexes which can reasonably be explained on the basis of electrostatic force between primary complex (metal in the case of binary complex) and secondary ligand, and space available to accommodate the secondary ligand. The stability decreases with the increase in ionic radii, i.e., Sc(III) > Y(III) > Sm(III) > Nd(III) > Pr(III) > La(III). In terms of secondary ligand, it follows the order PYC > GA > PYG. Rare earths form only 1 : 1 binary complex, and 1 : 1 : 1 mixed ligand complex in all the cases.

In recent years, the formation of complexes containing two different ligands has become of great interest to coordination chemists. In our previous papers we have reported some rare earth complexes of 1, 2-dihydroxybenzene 3, 5-disulphonic acid¹ (trivial name Tiron) and 2, 3-dihydroxynaphthalene 6-sulphonic acid² with EDTA as primary ligand. As an extension of our work, same technique has been applied to the complexes of Sc(III), Y(III), La(III), Pr(III), Nd(III) and Sm(III) with Nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) as primary ligand and Pyrocatechol (PYC), Pyrogallol (PYG) and Gallic acid (GA) as secondary ligands. For comparison purposes, study has been extended to the binary complexes under identical conditions.

Irving-Rossotti's pH-titration technique³ has been used to evaluate the stability constants of the binary as well as ternary complexes. The technique is similar to that used by Munshi *et al.*^{4,5} and Bhattacharya *et al.*^{6,7,8}.

Experimental

The chemicals used during the study were of analytical grade and were prepared in CO₂ free double distilled water as described in earlier papers^{9,10}. Instrumental set up and method used were same as earlier^{1,2}.

Results and Discussion

'Practical' Proton-ligand, metal-secondary ligand (binary) and mixed-ligand (ternary) stability constants were determined by the methods of interpolation at various \bar{n} -values (Method A) and at half \bar{n} -

values (Method B) as described in earlier papers^{9,10}, which are tabulated in Tables 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SECONDARY LIGAND AT 30° AT AN IONIC STRENGTH OF 0.2 M NaClO₄

Ligand	Method	log K ₁ ^H	log K ₂ ^H	log K ₃ ^H	log β ^H
PYC	A	11.64	9.07	—	20.71
	B	11.67	9.12	—	20.79
PYG	A	10.98	8.82	—	19.80
	B	10.95	8.87	—	19.82
GA	A	11.28	8.74	4.25	24.27
	B	11.26	8.70	4.27	24.23

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE BINARY METAL-SECONDARY LIGAND COMPLEXES (1 : 1) AT 30° AT AN IONIC STRENGTH OF 0.2 M NaClO₄

Metal	M(III)-PYC		M(III)-PYG		M(III)-GA	
	A	B	A	B	A	B
Sc(III)	14.20	14.16	14.79	14.76	16.62	16.59
Y(III)	9.81	9.85	10.68	10.66	12.59	12.55
La(III)	7.81	7.88	9.14	9.12	11.23	11.19
Pr(III)	8.60	8.66	9.99	9.93	12.08	12.04
Nd(III)	8.90	8.85	10.12	10.05	12.17	12.14
Sm(III)	9.29	9.27	10.57	10.53	12.48	12.48

TABLE 3—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE TERNARY COMPLEXES (1 : 1 : 1) AT 30° AT AN IONIC STRENGTH OF 0.2M NaClO₄

Metal	M(III)-NTA-PYC		M(III)-NTA-PYG		M(III)-NTA-GA	
	A	B	A	B	A	B
Sc(III)	10.69	10.72	10.56	10.52	10.68	10.65
Y(III)	7.74	7.78	7.34	7.32	7.68	7.63
La(III)	5.16	5.18	4.87	4.83	4.98	4.99
Pr(III)	6.33	6.35	5.76	5.73	6.01	5.98
Nd(III)	6.60	6.56	5.84	5.81	6.14	6.11
Sm(III)	6.98	7.01	6.45	6.39	6.70	6.66

* Present address : National Environmental Engineering Research Institute, Nehru Marg, Nagpur-440 020.

** Reader in Inorganic Chemistry, L. I. T., Nagpur University, Nagpur (for correspondence).

The formation curves in the case of binary complexes reveal formation of only 1 : 1 complex. Also in the case of ternary complexes, in spite of using excess of secondary ligand so as to attach maximum number of molecules of secondary ligand to the primary complex, value of \bar{n} never exceeded 1 which shows the formation of only 1 : 1 : 1 complex. In all the cases, the stability of mixed ligand complex was found to be much less than the corresponding binary complex which can be explained on the basis of electrostatic force between primary complex (metal in the case of binary complex) and secondary ligand and space available to accommodate the secondary ligand.

The stability of the binary as well as ternary complex decreases with the increase in ionic radii, i.e., $\text{Sc(III)} > \text{Y(III)} > \text{Sm(III)} > \text{Nd(III)} > \text{Pr(III)} > \text{La(III)}$ and in terms of secondary ligand follows the order $\text{PYC} > \text{GA} > \text{PYG}$.

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